

REDACTED

From: REDACTED
Sent: Friday, 18 March, 2022 16:26
To: security@yubico.com
Cc: REDACTED; CVE Request
Subject: FW: CVE ID for Service Request 1210428
Attachments: yubico.zip
Signed By: REDACTED

Importance: High

Hello,

I am writing to you to report a security vulnerability in the Yubico OTP Validation Server. I assess the severity NOT to be High, mostly because Yubico OTP isn't as widely used as the alternatives, such as U2f, FIDO etc., but regardless I believe it must be published and an advisory issued.

The product claims made on the product page state that the Yubico OTPs are hardware bound and unclonable. This might be correct AFTER the configuration has been written to the device. But, someone could make a duplicate device using the same configuration. After reprogramming, the new configuration will have to be uploaded to the Yubico servers. I have shown that the server will accept any uploaded configuration and, even though the upload form asks for the serial number, it is not utilized to make sure that the configuration is actually bound to a particular device.

The conclusion is that only OTPs starting with "cc" are hardware bound, since they are programmed at the factory. In the case where the customer wants to program custom secrets, the new configuration uploaded to the Yubico server (OTPs starting with "vv") are not hardware bound and the serial number isn't checked.

I have already applied for a CVE ID (CVE-2022-24584) but haven't otherwise publicized these findings and I leave it to you.

Thank you,
REDACTED

From: REDACTED REDACTED@mitre.org
Sent: Friday, 18 March, 2022 11:48
To: REDACTED
Cc: CVE Request <CVE-Request@mitre.org>
Subject: CVE ID for Service Request 1210428

Hello,

For the following CVE ID request, please see:

**** RESERVED **** Incorrect access control in Yubico OTP functionality of the YubiKey hardware tokens along with the Yubico OTP validation server. The Yubico OTP supposedly creates hardware bound second factor credentials. When a user reprograms the OTP functionality by "writing" it on a token using the Yubico Personalization Tool, they can then upload the new configuration to Yubicos OTP validation servers.

Please use CVE-2022-24584

This item will remain reserved pending a publicly available reference regarding the vulnerability itself, as well as the software version number.

REDACTED

Senior Cyber Vulnerability Assessment Engineer
CVE Content Team

REDACTED

REDACTED

From: **REDACTED** @yubico.com
Sent: Wednesday, 20 April, 2022 01:28
To: **REDACTED**
Cc: security@yubico.com
Subject: Re: FW: CVE ID for Service Request 1210428

Hi **REDACTED**,

Thank you for your patience here, and apologies for the wait.

The OTP seeds that we're referencing as being securely stored in a key are OTP seeds that are created by Yubico at key production time. These seeds are not duplicated between keys. Our users have the option to overwrite these seeds with customized seeds that they generate. Protection of these seed values then becomes the responsibility of the user, they can however also be uploaded to our Yubicloud OTP validation service as you have shown in your attached images to use our hosted OTP validation service.

I do not see this as a vulnerability of the Yubikey as the seed values have been duplicated to another key from a known source, not extracted from the key while under protection. This is much the same logic that one would apply to RSA secret keys if one already had possession of the secret value itself versus extracting the secret key by looking at ciphertext.

I would like to hear more about your proposed threat model if you disagree.

Thank you,

REDACTED

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REDACTED
REDACTED

Yubico Enterprise Security | [Yubico](#)

On Tue, Apr 19, 2022 at 2:43 PM **REDACTEDREDACTED** wrote:
Hello,

Any updates about my report? How are you going to proceed?

Thanks

Get [Outlook for Android](#)

From: **REDACTEDREDACTED**
Sent: Friday, March 18, 2022, 17:03
To: **REDACTED** @yubico.com
Subject: RE: FW: CVE ID for Service Request 1210428

Thanks for your response. Unfortunately, I don't have a PGP key, but you can use my S/MIME certificate for the same purpose

From: **REDACTED** @yubico.com
Sent: Friday, 18 March, 2022 16:58
To: **REDACTEDREDACTED**

Cc: security@yubico.com; **REDACTED** @mitre.org CVE Request <cve-request@mitre.org>
Subject: Re: FW: CVE ID for Service Request 1210428

Good Day **REDACTED**,

Thank you for your report and notification to Yubico Enterprise Security.
I will be looking deeper into this information and I, or someone else on my team, will reply to you directly with follow-up questions and feedback.

For reference, our rating system and public openPGP key is listed here on the Yubico website:
<https://www.yubico.com/support/security-advisories/issue-rating-system/>

Do you have a PGP key that we can use for future encrypted communications on this topic?

Thank you,
REDACTED

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REDACTED
REDACTED
Yubico Enterprise Security | [Yubico](#)

On Fri, Mar 18, 2022 at 8:26 AM **REDACTEDREDACTED** wrote:

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Senior Cyber Vulnerability Assessment Engineer

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